

The Mid-Scale Observatories Program

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Under the new NOIRLab organization, the Mid-Scale Observatories (MSO), a Program of NSF's NOIRLab, encompasses both Kitt Peak National Observatory and Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory. The core of the MSO Program is carried out on the four 4m-class telescopes: Victor M. Blanco and Southern Astrophysical Research (SOAR) in the south and Nicholas U. Mayall and WIYN in the north. Recent upgrades to instrumentation and operations, driven by scientific demands, have brought each of these no-longer-young telescopes exciting new capabilities.

The Dark Energy Camera (DECam) is a leading wide-field imager. Its >3-square-degree field is enabling breakthrough science from the Blanco on subjects ranging from Solar System rocks to the most distant quasars. With the deployment of AEON, the dynamic scheduling and observing program on SOAR, observers are following up transient alerts in the practice of Time Domain and Multi-Messenger Astronomy. DESI, the Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument, with its 5,000 fiber positioners, is poised to begin its five-year mission at the Mayall telescope to make the most detailed map of the Universe to date. NEID, the precision RV spectrometer on WIYN, is aiming to achieve state-of-the-art precision in exoplanet radial velocities, hopefully leading to the characterization of Earth-like planets in other solar systems.

MSO's mission includes providing a platform for scientific research and education carried out by the many tenants on both Kitt Peak and Cerro Tololo. These tenants contribute not only to the day-to-day operation of the mountain facilities through use fees but also to the scientific environment at the observatories, through their research and educational activities. Tenants often bring added value when they take on operation of telescopes, as in the recent roboticizing of the KPNO 2.1m Telescope on Kitt Peak by a group at Caltech.

The MSO Program is funded both publicly and privately. Blanco operations are still funded by the NSF's NOIRLab core agreement with NSF, as is the NOIRLab's share of SOAR operations. Mayall operations will be funded by the DOE Office of Science for the duration of the DESI survey. The NOIRLab share of WIYN is funded through a separate agreement with NSF, and NEID is operated under the NN-EXPLORE program, a joint NASA-NSF research initiative on exoplanets that is also funding exoplanet RV work with CHIRON at SMARTS in the south.

Taken as a group, the 4m telescopes making up the core of the MSO Program are helping drive some of the most exciting areas of astrophysics, and they demonstrate that well-built telescopes, if instrumented with new technology, can have very long and productive lives.

NEID Exoplanet Instrument Sees First Light

nationalastro.org/news/neid-exoplanet-instrument-sees-first-light/

DESI's 5000 Eyes Open as Kitt Peak Telescope Prepares to Map Space and Time

nationalastro.org/news/desi-5000-eyes-open-as-kitt-peak-telescope-prepares-to-map-space-and-time/

Automated Observing Network Inaugurated at SOAR Telescope

nationalastro.org/news/noao-automated-observing-network-inaugurated-at-soar-telescope/